

The Experience Of Learners' Thinking Autonomy In Rwanda. A Phenomenological Study Of Tutors' Implementation Of Competence Based Curriculum

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Abstract

Purpose and Methodology: using a phenomenological perspective as both the theoretical and methodological framework, this study investigates how TTC (Teacher Training College) Tutors with a community mode of thinking from a Rwandan context, facilitate and experience learners' individual thinking autonomy where this autonomy is understood as thinking and deciding with self-governed principles for learning. 24 TTC tutors from 4 provinces were observed and given an interview to share their experience on how they facilitate thinking autonomy for their learners.

Findings: Tutors' implementation of the current competence-based curriculum, which embraces Learner Centered Pedagogy (LCP), revealed that learner centered pedagogy is not properly adapted to the Rwandan situation which is an African context, because LCP is rooted in Western culture influenced by the Cartesian philosophy, characterized by an individual personal reasoning. Thinking autonomy understood in the Kantian connotation was not found in Rwandan classes because individual learners seemed to use a community thinking schema which originates from their social context. Findings were interpreted by the researcher with phenomenology that describes first-hand tutors' and researcher's narratives of how they experience the paradox and dichotomy of facilitating thinking autonomy for learners who have evolved within a community paradigm of thought.

Within the Rwandan context, community thinking paradigms seem to take precedence over the individual thinking autonomy, which opposes the implementation of curriculum intending the facilitation of individual thinking autonomy according to western Cartesian philosophical culture.

Unique contribution to theory, practice and policy: This research intends to benefit both the Ministry and its stakeholders in education and schools in a special way as a platform for reflecting on how to implement CBC, taking into account the cultural context of Rwanda which in one way or another should determine the mode of thinking that is locally effective. This ideal fits into the mission statement and the general goal of the Rwandan Government which seeks to create a knowledge based economy, to reduce poverty and improve the well-being of its people. By that the Government intends to fight ignorance and illiteracy and to avail human resources capable of carrying out the socio-economic development of Rwanda in a knowledge based economy (Aubert, 2018).

Introduction

Rwandan TTC (Teacher Training Colleges) tutors are trained in Competence Based Curriculum which requires them to facilitate learners' thinking autonomy. They have been selected as respondents to this study which adopts phenomenology both as a theoretical framework and as a method that describes and interprets their experience of Competence Based Curriculum. This curriculum advocates for a pedagogy that has multiple applications, of which only the aspect of facilitating learners' autonomous thinking was retained in this study. Thinking autonomy in this study is understood as the capacity to self regulate one's own mental and conscious activities, processes of knowing including reasoning, judging without any external constraint.

While some description is done with concepts from the Husserlian phenomenology (McConnell-Henry et al., 2009), this study puts emphasis on the Heideggerian existential phenomenology and the Gadamer's hermeneutic phenomenology (Weis, 2001) in order to include the possibility of historical, cultural and contextual interpretation of tutors' experience of facilitating students' thinking autonomy. This article embraces the Heideggerian role of *aletheia*, which means the disclosure of that which is hidden (Serafin, 2016), namely about

the Tutor's facilitation of students' thinking autonomy. A thematic classification was made by grouping, describing and analyzing similar experiences in order to reveal the essence (or nature) of tutors' experience. This study is interested in the understanding of the phenomenological truth regarding the everydayness of TTC tutors stories about facilitating thinking autonomy in the Rwandan context.

Aims of the investigation

Using different phenomenological approaches including both the transcendental, the hermeneutic and the existential phenomenology perspectives, the Heideggerian Dasein, which means being in the world, this study aims at investigating the experiences of TTC tutors in the world of their students' thinking autonomy. The study investigates how the tutors' pedagogical relations with their students triggers the empowerment of the latter with the capacity to think by themselves (thinking autonomy). The description of common and constant patterns arising from their stories were described and interpreted.

Background to the study

Governments across Sub-Saharan Africa, Rwanda included have adopted Learner Centered Pedagogy (LCP) as the official teaching method at all levels of formal education (van de Kuilen et al., 2019; Tadesse et al., 2021). Rwanda took the path of CBC (Competence Based Curriculum) (Tabaro, 2018) which in this study is like a branch of LCP. These policy decisions were shaped in response to both the global political economy and local circumstances (Altinyelken, 2010).

The major aims of Education in Rwanda include both giving to all Rwandans knowledge, skills, values to become good citizens and to improve the quality of their lives. Education thus stands as a fundamental right with the double mission of ensuring human resource development and poverty reduction (Mineduc, 2018). Only competent teachers capacitated with knowledge, skills, attitudes and values can achieve these goals and fulfill appropriately their citizenship responsibilities (Mineduc, 2007). To achieve these ends at classroom level, CBC is one of the strategies that have been recommended within Rwandan policies despite the challenge posed by shortages of sufficiently qualified teachers.

The current policy considers CBC (Tabaro, 2018), a learnercentred pedagogy, the best pedagogy to be used in classrooms grounding on the premise that it can help to achieve educational goals and maximize the learning outcome better than any other approach. It is grounded on the idea that learning takes place effectively when students participate actively in their learning by trial and error, collaboration, interaction, inquiry, creativity, individual or group projects and initiatives where the learner is actively engaged in the process of learning. That is why it is sometimes called active pedagogy as opposed to passive reception of knowledge (Normand, 2017).

Among the assumptions of Learner Centered Pedagogies, CBC included, there is a belief that these approaches strengthen student control over learning processes by equipping the learner with great autonomy as learners to face the world's challenges. Students acquire responsibility for their own learning. In addition, it assumes that these approaches promote competence acquisition and critical thinking through peer communication, discovery and learning. This approach leads students to reflect on what they are learning and how they are learning it, equipping them with skills on how to think, solve problems, evaluate evidence, analyze arguments, and generate hypotheses. They produce all those learning skills essential to mastering material in the discipline. These approaches are considered to be the best for teaching because they contribute to developing learner autonomy understood in the Kantian meaning of intellectual autonomy as a self-governing principle or else an intellectual self-direction (Carter, 2020) which is a mark of educational maturity and readiness to face the world's challenges, without necessarily excluding the incorporation of other people's views in one's own autonomy.

Problem statement

Ideally, CBC has the same features as other Learner Centered Pedagogies (LCP) and is believed to focus on the very final cause of education, that of capacitating the learner with thinking and problem-solving skills. However, in the midst of widespread emphasis on LCP as a universally relevant model of teaching for the 21st century, growing evidence suggests that the approach is not being easily understood, accepted, and implemented at the classroom level (Tabulawa, 2003; Vavrus, 2008). There seems to be a lack of consensus whether policy changes that adopted the approach are achieving the desired economic, political, and pedagogical outcomes within the context of implementation of such an approach (African context and Rwanda in particular). It is also unknown whether CBC is understood, accepted or used by tutors for student learning to think independently. This study therefore raises the question of how Rwandan CBC implementation within classrooms generates thinking autonomy among learners who belong to a different mode of reasoning culture than the Western type. Although, it is stated within the curriculum that learners will be capable of independent reasoning, there is no evidence that links this outcome to the immediate classroom interaction between teacher and learners. There is no evidence indicating that thinking autonomy in the Kantian meaning takes place among Rwandan learners because of CBC.

Within the Rwandan context, there seems to be no evidence that individual tutors' prefer LCP to traditional lecture methods which are a tutor-centered approach commonly called the authoritarian approach. There seems to be no evidence indicating that the use of LCP approaches is appropriate or whether it produces the expected results in this African context.

The problem for sub-Saharan Africa and Rwanda in Particular is that CBC (a teaching method originating from Western liberal thinking philosophy) doesn't seem to flow from the local cultural settings where tutors' community rules and customs seem to dominate individual initiatives. On one hand CBC requires adopting the Western concepts of autonomy, freedom and equality between tutor and learners in order to allow learners to express themselves as partners and not as subjects to the teacher. On the other hand, the tutors using this same approach are products of a society characterized by hierarchy, obedience to authority, where every member of society knows the customs, the role and rank conferred to them and ought not to challenge those who are in a position of authority. In some traditional African contexts, children, younger persons or individuals in lower social and economic status (juniors) are sometimes considered as receivers of wisdom and elders or those in higher position of authority (seniors) as sources of wisdom, truth and authority. Seniors seem to like and hold their status of unquestionable authority in a way that the logical fallacies of argumentum ad baculum (Appeal to elderliness; appeal to tradition) and argumentum ad verecundiam (appeal to authority) may seem irrelevant and ridiculous to them because elders and experts (seniors or authority in a specific domain) may in most cases be considered source of truth (Tabulawa, 2013). Although such a context cannot be claimed to represent the Rwandan context in its complex totality, it seems however to share a number of aspects to a great extent.

In most African cultures a vertical chain of authority cuts across the hierarchies defined within society. Each member of the society is placed without ambiguity within a given social position, while roles assigned to each are clearly defined. Members are expected to conform to their cultural obligations like obeying commands and instructions even when this goes against their individual choices. The person is expected to respect such an arrangement so long as their superior (sometimes elders, parents, employers, high ranked personnel, teachers, experts...) are in command. Developing pupils' personal thinking autonomy in the above conditions seems almost excluded from such a cultural context, since the achievement of personal autonomy contradicts the supremacy of the community over the individual goals and challenges the cultural and traditional authority of those in position of power over their subjects, parents over their wards and teacher over learners—no matter how old they might be (Indabawa, 2003).

The reason why it is important to research on the above problem is that, assumptions which ascertain the effectiveness of CBC may lead to pseudo teaching and learning, missing thus the purpose for which teaching and learning take place, if a clear understanding of the interplay between this approach and the context in which it is being applied are not revealed.

This research will explore such contradictory experiences by answering to the following research questions:

Research questions

General research question: How does CBC implementation by tutors generate student thinking autonomy?

- What are TTC tutors' personal experiences (stories, narratives, beliefs) of their facilitation of learners' thinking autonomy?
- How do tutors implement CBC to capacitate students to think for themselves?
- How does tutors' social cultural background influence their implementation of LCP?

Research Objectives

- To identify how TTC tutors' use CBC in their interaction with learners.
- To describe and analyze tutors' experience of helping learners to think by themselves.
- To identify elements of the social contexts that may influence the facilitation of thinking autonomy.

Literature review

For John Dewey, learners' thinking is essential to education when learners are given freedom to discuss on equal opportunity (Synytsia, 2020). Regardless of which approach a teacher chooses to use, education cannot avoid the mandate to facilitate learner's autonomy of reasoning, and foster personal ability through learning experiences.

Learning takes place through reconstructing and reorganizing experience to increase the ability to direct subsequent experience by the use of thinking which transforms an individual into a problem solver and responsible citizen (Weiler & Weiler, 2011).

The CBC approach is among other approaches, a means to education, a means of thinking and acting not an end in itself. As such, like all other means, it should aim to serve education in the best possible way to solve existing problems and challenges within society. However, from the perspective of the philosophy of education, it cannot be avoided to interrogate the approach regarding whether the Rwandan pedagogical context is adequate to stimulate thinking in which learning brings solutions to existing problems. Much more thinking seems to be required in classrooms of a developing country which moreover has a vision of a knowledge-based economy because knowledge is bridged by thinking.

In an African context like Rwanda, how tutors stimulate learner's autonomy remains a problem to be addressed. Autonomy of thinking as an educational goal cannot be taken for granted as being a universal, culture-free value which all societies pursue easily through their respective educational systems without the need for contextualization. In societies that are less inclined towards the values of western free equalitarian civilizations within which the idea of personal autonomy of thinking is encased, learner autonomy as an aim of education seems merely an interesting theoretical proposition. This is because, reasoning structures are not strictly a neutral affair, they are also rooted in the contexts which are referred to and teachers are no exception to this (Kleinig, 2016).

Nothing indeed should be taken for granted as a matter of truth. There are reasons to doubt when an educational or a teaching approach (in this case CBC) is assumed to possess a universal culture free validity in capacitating students to think for themselves. Descartes rightly suggested in his quest for certainty to leave no stone unturned when carrying out a knowledge investigation. That is why this study chose phenomenology as a special methodology for investigating the truth about human beings, because when subjects become "objects" of study, there should necessarily be a difference in the process of knowing them. In this regard the French existential philosopher Henri Bergson said approximately this: mathematical problems are solved with objective measurable solutions. Yet, a human being is not a problem but a mystery. A different method other than the positivistic approach is therefore needed and this research uses phenomenology as an appropriate method for investigating human experience. This approach is a neighbor to other approaches in the contemporary philosophy including post-modernism, post-positivism and post-structuralism.

Phenomenology

Phenomenology is the study of the structure of active or passive conscious experience from the subjective first person point of view. It explores the phenomenal appearance in our human experience. It is the study of phenomena (appearance) or reality in our conscious experience. It is the study of meaning things have in our human experience, their underlying order, their content that is either static representing unchanging perceptual properties or the generic content that emerges into our conscious awareness over time (perception, memory, imagination, intuition, thinking, signification...). It describes the meaning, the significance of objects, events, tools, flow of time, self and others as they arise, as they are experienced in our life-world (Heidegger). It is the study of the meaning things have in the individual's consciousness. It is an alternative view to rationalism which deals with the objective world of things while phenomenology belongs to the experiential world of phenomena in human consciousness. It studies consciousness and how this interacts with phenomena presented to it, the object of consciousness (Dowling, 2007).

Berrios (1989) considers phenomenology as an umbrella term covering doctrines that loosely share on the one hand metaphysical assumptions of what the world is for individuals and epistemological standpoints on how the world can be known. On the other hand, it concerns strategies for describing mental entities that relate to the world in question. All schools in phenomenology try to capture the essence of the lived experience of which the phenomenal reconstruct lies on a firm ground to show that the outcome of an experience is naturally greater than the sum of its parts.

In general, studies within phenomenological variations may include description, interpretation, analysis, logico-semantic significance, experiential paradigms of cognitive neuroscience, depending on the school of phenomenology. This research will not explore in detail all phenomenological approaches but will focus particularly on the transcendental and the existential phenomenology defended respectively by Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger (McConnell-Henry et al., 2009). That said however, there are common notions that are crosscutting among the different approaches of phenomenology, which will be used along this article.

Basic concepts in Phenomenology

From an epistemological question of how do I know what I know, phenomenology defies natural science. The latter claims to know the world as it is excluding the human subject input; phenomenology on the other hand, challenges this scientific view: no knowledge is possible without the consideration of the knower, the human consciousness which decides what has meaning or not. It is in this regard that concepts described below, constitute the structure of human consciousness according to phenomenology. Before knowing the object, it is necessary to understand the structure of the human consciousness which is the foundation of all that human beings can possibly know.

Consciousness

Consciousness is an essential mental structure in which every human experience about existence can be shaped. It characterizes probably the very essence of a human being as a thinking subject (Radner, 1988). However the existence of consciousness poses a problem: Is the subject or self an entity that is constant despite continuous changes which affect consciousness? Is the adult human the same as during infancy? Is consciousness a thing (a substance)? Is consciousness an act, a way of being in the world? Is consciousness sufficient in defining what a human being is? For both Spinoza and Sigmund Freud, consciousness is the weakest activity of human beings because human fundamental existence is mostly dominated by unconsciousness (Vermorel, 2009). How can we then account for any possibility of knowing if we are not conscious of what determines our experience?

Consciousness may refer to either spontaneous (awareness of the outside world) or reflective consciousness (awareness of our own mental processes). Unlike objects which are determined by their material properties, human subjects live a different experience as free beings that change and choose what to become according to most existentialists. A subject cannot be locked within an identity, as it is the case for an object which exists as an "itself" according to Sartre and determined by its material properties. According to Sartre, a human subject is a project not an object. It cannot be said of a human being that s/he is for example egoistic forever. This state can change by virtue of human capacity to determine who to become (Çelebi, 2014).

In the sense above it can even be said that only consciousness exists in that to exist means etymologically to come out of self. While objects don't exist, because they insist in faithfulness to their original properties, in not changing their identity by remaining what they are, our ability to become distant from self the way humans do can be seen as a fundamental relationship between our being in the world and our consciousness of this.

For the human subject, existence therefore is connected to the problem of freedom. This is the human way of transcending oneself to become more and different from the previous self. In this respect, Nietzsche introduces the concept of the will to power that brings one to always surpass oneself in a continuous search for superiority (the superman) although this is not the only purpose of human freedom.

Thus, a human being can be defined only in a provisional temporal manner, waiting necessarily for a new becoming that relates to our shared experience of being. Describing thus a human being in an absolute or final way is to define her as an object. A stone can be identified by its properties every time but a human being cannot be limited within unchanging characteristics. If a human being is locked in a definition, Sartre calls this way, "chosifier", literally to consider her as an object because it is equivalent to denying them the freedom which carries them always away from themselves and that specifies them as human species. The very essence of human being cannot be confined in fixed properties but in a changing perfectible identity by virtue of freedom to make oneself or loose oneself in a dynamic being that is always other than its past self through conscious choices and actions. Consciousness therefore is the most important aspect of human essence as a knower different from other animal species; it is the source and foundation of all that a human can claim to know and communicate.

In his search for knowledge and certainty, René Descartes central analysis of consciousness serves him as the point of departure. In order to reach certainty, he proceeds by what he called a methodic doubt, a provisional doubt used as a method (Descartes, 2014) different from skeptical doubt which is a permanent doubt aiming at doubting because according to its proponents, knowledge is inaccessible and cannot be attained (Machuca, 2011). That is why sceptics preferred the suspension of judgment to gain the peace of mind (Ataraxy) rather than trying to search for knowledge one can never reach. For sceptics, humans can only gain access to the reasonable or the probable. Protagoras said in this regard that nothing exists, if it existed, I cannot know it and if I knew it, I cannot talk about it. Unlike this skeptical view, methodic doubt is a method of provisionally suspending judgment until certainty is reached. It is a tactical doubt and a strategy to reach knowledge certainty. Descartes within his meditations begins to doubt all traditional knowledge he had acquired until then. He uses the principle of doubting everything that has no evidence of clear and distinct ideas. The only remaining certainty which survives doubting everything else is the "Cogito ergo sum", I think therefore I am. If everything can be doubted, one however, cannot doubt that there is someone doubting, and that is the doubting subject, or the conscious subject.

From Descartes perspective, the cogito inaugurates consciousness of the subject as the most certain aspect of knowing. Although ancient philosophy talked about it under different terms, the problem of consciousness was

clearly inaugurated by Descartes and has in one way or another dominated the epistemological debate of modern philosophy in general and phenomenology in particular.

It is in this regard that Edmund Husserl said that the task of philosophy is to describe the content of consciousness or to describe what appears to our consciousness regardless of whether others regard this content as true or not. Every consciousness is consciousness of something, it intends to think about something, it aims at an object (intentionality). Husserl poses a critique to Descartes conception of consciousness as an object. Consciousness is not an object but rather an act from which originates the meaning of everything that can be known or described by the subject. Descartes presents us with a consciousness that can exist independently from the material world. Heidegger's *dasein* brings it back to the world since *dasein* means being in the world. Husserl puts the world between parenthesis (bracketing) in order to investigate consciousness structures. This bracketing of the material world is not the same as excluding it but putting it aside for examining what happens in human consciousness. Edmund corrects Descartes by defining consciousness as an act, an intentionality directed towards an object but not an object itself (Husserl, 1931).

Intentionality

Intentionality is part of the fundamental structure of consciousness and the idea that consciousness is consciousness of something. It acts and aims at an object (any content, true or false, real or apparent). A human consciousness is always aware of something. Intentionality transcends the perception of a single perspective and embraces the total meaning of the object (or the phenomena or the idea).

Intentionality is an act in itself and it points to a meaning. It is referential by nature. This is therefore a two-fold actional (noesis) and referential (noema) consciousness structure, pointing at a particular content (Heidegger, 1970). Experiences such as higher order perceptions of one's mind's operations and mental activities such as perception, imagination, thought, emotion, desire, volition, action are part of the structure. These active or passive dispositions are all shaped by the individual motor skills, habits, social background, cultural context and language as it appears within Heidegger and Gadamer's accounts (Weis, 2001). Intentionality constitutes the most important structure of consciousness. In Phenomenology, intentionality is an act or a reference towards an object or a content of a particular nature which is different from the object of natural science. This notion is captured within Husserl's description of reduction or bracketing.

Description and Reduction

Description of phenomena is the aim of phenomenology while reduction is synonymous to "bracketing" or suspending judgment or else in the technical concept of "epoché" in order to let things return in their pure and original state (Overgaard, 2002). Phenomenology aims at uncovering the hidden meaning and essences of an experience.

For Husserl, the method of phenomenology consists of "bracketing", or the Greek "epoché" which also is a synonym for reduction. Idetic reduction aims at the essence of the phenomenon. This is made possible by the technique called 'imaginary variation', which varies all the possible attributes of the phenomenon in order to distinguish the contingent from the necessary part of the phenomenon as experienced in the first person.

Natural science studies the physical world and phenomena in an objective way independent of the subject's opinions and personal considerations. This scientific assumption is what Husserl calls the "natural attitude". Husserl's transcendental phenomenology takes seriously the effort to "bracket" or to "temporarily suspend" this "natural attitude", in order to "come back to things themselves" or to study the subject consciousness, through which to apprehend the essence of consciousness.

Husserl's epistemology is trying to answer the question, how do I know something? In the knowing process that brings the subject and the object into relationship, the starting point should be the knowledge of the consciousness of this subject. Natural science excludes the subject for the sake of objectivity. Husserl takes the opposite path to that of natural science for which objects and the world are known as they are. While natural science brackets the subject for the sake of objectivity, Husserl brackets the belief in the objective knowledge of the world because this belief excludes and ignores the conscious subject who plays a fundamental role in this epistemological exercise.

Husserl attempts to describe the knower's conscious structures with certainty, so as to demonstrate later that knowledge depends very much on the subjective conscious structures which determine through intentionality the meaning of the phenomenon. In this regard, knowledge is a product of the hyphen between subject-object and not a result of one of them excluding the other. Husserl shows that before knowing anything at all, we must know the structures of consciousness. How does this knowing faculty proceed? What are its fundamental features from which we can claim to know anything? These are the questions Husserl was trying to answer. His initiative is different from disbelieving in this "natural attitude". It only suspends it for the purpose of going back to the originality of things. It is about marking our perimeter of everything that is part of the natural attitude. This is what he calls the eidetic reduction (eidos = essence), which permits the description of features

of our experience that are both necessary and invariant. However, Husserl died before exploring the object side. He had focused on the description of the subject.

The essence

The essence unifies all aspects of the structure of consciousness including intentionality, reduction, bracketing and epoche (Butler, 2016). It is the core or the main meaning of an experience by an individual or a group, which makes it what it is. It is about what it means to be something in general terms. However essence in phenomenological eidetic reduction refers to the metaphysical essence of an experience which aims at the intuition of a meaning using imaginary variations. This exercise is facilitated by questions such as: what is necessary for something to be perceived as that thing? At which point does this or that become not that thing? These are examples of questions that lead to the experience of “back to the things themselves”. The study of phenomenology is enriched by the exploration of many schools and variations from which we retain few. More themes will be explored in different schools of phenomenology.

Different schools in Phenomenology

Schools that include transcendental, hermeneutic and existential phenomenology have been often mentioned in this area of study. Husserl defended the transcendental school. Heidegger moved attention from essences and consciousness of phenomena to hermeneutic (interpretative, meaning assigning) and existential dimensions (Finlay, 2009).

Transcendental phenomenology

According to Husserl, who started this school, we are always already in the world and the only certainty we have is our own experience of the world. Understanding the structure of human consciousness becomes therefore the foundation of all that we can know (Husserl, 1970). The main assumption in transcendental phenomenology is that the basic assumptions of an individual need to be transcended in order to capture original reality or “lived world”, first hand life experience. By suspending or bracketing personal opinion, or suspending the natural attitude or bracketing the scientific attitude (putting aside the attitude of considering the world as an objective entity that can be studied independently from the subject), it is possible to reach a single and essential description of phenomena. In the same way, existentialism sought to part away from traditional philosophy and science which focused on describing the objective world instead of being concerned with human existential conditions.

Existential phenomenology

A human being was defined in terms of rational capacities by the Cartesian philosophy. The rejection of this view by Blaise Pascal (1623-1662) and by Kierkegaard (1813-1855) who found both complexity of human experience and contradiction between mind and body paved a way to the rise of existential phenomenology. This school rejects the view that the aim of philosophy is to describe an objective, disinterested, detached and disengaged world from human everydayness. Some phenomena can reveal themselves only when an individual is engaged with life in the world in a specific manner (Skirke, 2014). They aim at reaching direct and primitive contact with the world through the description of everyday experience in the individual’s consciousness. They share the same view with hermeneutic phenomenology that “reduction” of phenomena” in the Husserlian way is impossible. MerleauPonty and Heidegger explored respectively the role of lived-body in perception and the meaning of being (Sadala & De Camargo Ferreira Adorno, 2002).

Hermeneutic phenomenology

Tenants of this school include Gadamer, Paul Ricoeur, Van Manen, Martin Heidegger and others (Farrell, 2020) Heidegger published “*History of concept of time (1925)*” and “*Being and Time (1927)*” where most explanation of the concept is found. For them, “bracketing” personal opinions is an impossible task, while the aim of hermeneutic phenomenology is to unveil individual’s or group’s experience through life world stories. They invest in the efforts to understand the subjective experience through interpretative narration and description to reach objective, authentic nature of phenomena as lived by an individual or a group.

Basic themes in hermeneutic phenomenology include “interpretation,” “textual meaning,” “dialogue,” “pre-understanding,” and “tradition.”

Paul Ricoeur, Heidegger and Gadamer, are often referred to as representatives of hermeneutic phenomenology. Phenomenology is said to be hermeneutical the moment its method is considered interpretive (not purely descriptive as Husserlian transcendental phenomenology). It is the work of Heidegger which shows that all attempt to describe phenomena is always already an interpretation. Every type of human awareness is already an interpretation. Heidegger praised art and poetry as the most expressive works which can serve as models for interpreting the essence of truth, being, thinking, language...

Gadamer a student to Heidegger analyzed the nature of questioning, the function of language, the meaning of prejudice, the subtleties of human conversation, the role of history, culture and tradition in the works of human understanding. It is Paul Ricoeur who examined how meaning is mediated and transferred through language (narration and storytelling), art, myth and religion and concluded that meanings are never given directly to our

understanding, that we must go through a hermeneutic detour via the symbolism of culture. He came back to the problem of being, of self and self-identity (Kaffle, 2013).

The birth of hermeneutic phenomenology

The purpose of hermeneutic phenomenology is to reflect upon and analyze lived meaning of basic human experience as it appears in the everydayness of life. Phenomenology arose from philosophy and became famous as a methodology in Edmund Husserl's works during the 19th century. Although his findings were debated, contested, modified, falsified many times, its authority in the field remains almost unquestionable. Many other philosophers are associated to its transformation from transcendental to hermeneutic phenomenology namely the German philosopher Martin Heidegger, the French philosopher Jean Paul Sartre, Maurice Merleau-Ponty, Jean Luc Nancy and Emmanuel Lévinas.

According to Van Manen (2014), the basic experience we have of the world is already full of meaning through history, culture and different human and non-human events. These phenomena precede anything we may understand, say or write about them. This explains why we are "already too late" in trying to explain phenomena that has taken place before we can even think about them. Accessing the original experience directly thus becomes a major challenge to hermeneutic phenomenology, yet this is the very object of our interest (Adams, 2014). Hermeneutic phenomenology works remain always contingent and incomplete although as a methodology it remains unique. Its newness is its very specific way of encountering the world and experiencing the uniqueness of phenomena in all its strangeness and complexity, which we afterwards translate into text that illuminates its meaning (Merleau-Ponty, 2006).

More particularly, hermeneutic phenomenology together with existential phenomenology are characterized by different concepts coined by Heidegger, which help to understand its distinctive features (Zuckerman, 2015):

Dasein

Dasein is the Heideggerian concept for "being there", a human reality. It can be understood passively as the fact of existing or actively as the act of existing and presence in the world. For Heidegger, dasein is the most fundamental essence of being human. It is manifested in different aspects which define its structure namely, "being in the world", "being with others", "temporality", "being for death", "angst". Being there is the essence of being human which at the same time transcends us and demarcates our existential horizons.

The human subject designated as dasein is shaped by temporality because of finitude and the aspiration to nothingness. It is a being for death open to finitude. Understanding the vulnerability of human condition and living with openness to nothingness is living an authentic life.

The essence of dasein

Being in the world

Dasein is irremediably always engaged in the world and cannot be conceived independent from it as it was the case for Descartes.

Being thrown in the world

A human being finds oneself already there without having chosen to be and obliged to cope with their existence such that no escape is provided because we are condemned to freedom, to the obligation to assign meaning and direction to our own existence. Jean Paul Sartre's existential philosophy explains more about this dimension.

Being with others

A human being lives in a world that precedes her, an already pre-established community with its culture, traditions and context. Whether we like it or not the other is present in every corner of our past, present and projected existence. We cannot escape from their influence which in some sense determines our intersubjective nature of being human.

Temporality

Being is existing in time, being shaped by a past, a being there now and moved by future projects and particularly concerned with the finitude, the contingency and the limitedness of this time.

Being for death

The final horizon of our existence is death. Finitude is the most accurate characterization of being human in the world.

Anguish

The constant preoccupation we have and the openness to our future nothingness form together the ultimate possibility of our existence as contingent, accidental and mortal beings.

Phenomenology is concerned with people's perception of the world in which they live everyday (Langridge, 2007). The main themes celebrated in phenomenology include, consciousness, intentionality, essences, description, reduction, dasein (Merleau-Ponty, 1962).

Difference between transcendental and hermeneutic Phenomenology

Phenomenology by Edmund Husserl seeks to give an account of the more precisely description of facts of human experience, the consciousness of phenomena (Stumpf, 1994). The perception of the object as we mean it (intentionality), or as we create or intend the phenomena in us. For Edmund Husserl, the world is nothing other than what I am aware of and what appears valid in my acts of thinking. The whole meaning and reality of the world rests exclusively on such acts of thinking. "I and my life remain- in my sense of reality- untouched by whichever way we decide the issue of whether the world is or is not" (Stumpf, 1994, p 488).

Unlike Husserl transcendental phenomenology which seeks to faithfully describe the original content of human consciousness, hermeneutic phenomenology represented by Heidegger denies the possibility of "bracketing" human content of the consciousness. In his hermeneutic phenomenology, he argues that any external intervention toward the reality of human consciousness is already an interpretation. The example of language used to communicate the content of consciousness can show that it is already an interpretation.

In terms of our subjective experience in transcendental phenomenology, what makes consciousness different from other types of efforts is that it gives an account of how noeses (the acts of the mind) and noemata (the contents of the mind to which it refers) cohere and unfold in ways that are both necessary and invariant (Rassi & Shahabi, 2015). The variation or not of meaning, is one of the breaking points between transcendental, hermeneutic phenomenology, and other types of phenomenology.

In this regard for example, the idea of intentionality creates three puzzles for Franz Brentano: 1. It is about relationships between subject and object but intentionality accepts even inexistent objects? 2. Is there a causal relationship between the subject and the object? 3. What is the ontological status of the object of intentionality? A. Is it physical? B. is it mental? This distinction (between A and B) creates respectively intentional realism (A: physical things) and intentional idealism (B: ideas, perceptions, representations, retreat to interiority).

Methodology

Participants' profile

24 teachers, from TTC (Tutor Training Colleges) were randomly selected to participate in this study, following the assumption that they received a similar pedagogical training before joining the teaching career.

Research paradigm

This study feeds on qualitative framework within relativistic paradigms and is opposed to positivism or the scientific method that seeks mathematically quantifiable magnitudes. It is aligned within the same trend as post-modernism, post-structuralism or post-positivism, where concepts and theories of phenomenological research approaches belong to (Finlay, 2013).

Instruments of data collection

An interview schedule was administered to 24 participants from 4 Teacher Training Colleges and 4 provinces followed by a classroom observation of teaching and learning facilitation in their respective classes. The research observed how the tutors implemented CBC (Competence Based Curriculum) in a way that their concern was or was not directed towards facilitating or allowing learners' thinking autonomy. Since this research is registered within the qualitative epistemological paradigm, natural science approaches were not needed for measurement and quantification. The research focused on attitudes, values, narrations expressed by tutors and students in a phenomenological language.

Data analysis techniques

A technique specific to phenomenology known as "horizontalization" was used. Similar significant statements were grouped into themes or text representing the same phenomenon: activity, concept or idea. Emerging code structures helped to reach textural description that unfolded into a structural description of the settings and context within which Rwandan tutors operate. It is the structural description that allowed the description and interpretation of the essence of Rwandan tutors' experience of learners' thinking autonomy.

Results

Tutors' experience of learners' thinking autonomy

Introduction

The following data analysis is based on data obtained through tutors' interview and from an observation checklist by the research. Focus was directed towards aspects of pedagogy that allowed learners' thinking autonomy. Epoché, which literally means suspension, helped the research to focus on personal and tutors experience of learners' thinking autonomy by bracketing all other scientific methods of data collection. This is what Husserl calls marking out the perimeter of everything that's part of the ordinary scientific attitude or the natural attitude. By epoché the researcher was enabled to inquire into the nature of tutors' teaching reality from the perspective of the "Phenomenological attitude" which analysed classroom experience in terms of the researcher's subjective experience regardless of what the policy or the academic theories suggest. This means in other words that this research was done in a purely ordinary manner of human day to day experience.

Focusing on thinking autonomy aspects, the researcher, started to notice how tutors implemented LCP. Things seemed very different from how he usually took them for granted. From the phenomenological standpoint, the meaning of teaching with LCP varies in some respects compared to when it is analyzed from the scientific standpoint or the natural attitude. The research therefore found some features of tutors and his personal experience that seemed both necessary and invariant in tutors' implementation of LCP for the facilitation of learners' thinking autonomy. These features included curriculum aspects, authority of the teacher and the cultural influence in teaching. The later aspect revealed how the Rwandan cultural context crosscuts all teaching and learning components namely, the curriculum, the content, the pedagogy, the attitudes of both teacher and learner in terms of their epistemological and metaphysical beliefs about what teaching and learning means and how to make them successful. The study revealed the essence of tutors' experience and how all these affected learners' thinking autonomy.

Curriculum and learner autonomy

The Rwandan curriculum describes some features that should characterize the relationship between the teacher and the learner regarding their thinking autonomy. However, results revealed that there is a gap and mismatch between the ideal concern of the curriculum or policy on one hand and the real classroom practice on the other hand. Thinking autonomy does not take place the way curriculum suggests.

The curriculum has emerged in a particular culture, the Rwandan culture. The researcher's experience observed that the Rwandan culture conception of teaching and learning is a top-down relationship of hierarchy between teacher and learner where the teacher is the initiator and the learner is the receiver. Data was analyzed from some of Freire's concepts of banking pedagogy while a phenomenological attitude was maintained throughout the analysis:

Teacher teaches and the learner listens with obedience

Although in the current Competence Based curriculum the relationship between the role of the teacher and that of the learner suggests a participative relationship, it did not seem evident that the traditional purpose of teacher namely the transmission of teachers' lectures into learners' minds has disappeared. This was evidenced by the attitudes of observed teachers: disregarding almost completely the learners' innovation outside the curriculum, discouraging every original idea that is not planned, favoring curriculum schedule over learners' needs and dreams, the consideration of learners as children who cannot plan for themselves and for whom the school should plan. Confirmation was made by data from interview where the following statement represents other similar statements:

"The curriculum is not set in a way to respect learners' view. In no way it inspires teachers to respect learners' views and capacitate students to think for themselves. Pressure from school authorities to implement the planned content push me to obey without refusing. The Head teacher comes and say: I want you to cover this. Instead of letting learners reach autonomy, you have to finish teaching the content to satisfy your boss and the public."

This statement was verified by the researcher's observation which sought to understand whether students' ideas that are not in conformity with the curriculum could be retained by the teacher as part of the learning content. The scale of the observation made by the research consisted of determining whether the feature being observed was "present", or "absent". In all the cases observed, students' ideas were rejected if they were not in conformity with the curriculum.

It didn't seem useless to note that only curriculum content was retained for learning while original ideas from learners could be considered ceremonial because learners provided their ideas in class but these ideas did not appear in their notebooks that contained things to learn for evaluation. Interview confirmed this point when a tutor said:

“...The teacher prepares and sets criteria. The curriculum indicates how evaluation should take place and the teachers follow instructions...”

A second observation confirms that innovation and creativity from learners could not be accepted beyond what the teacher permitted according to curriculum instructions. Only 8% observed cases showed that the teacher permitted creativity and innovation but if and only if they were related to curriculum requirements.

Observation in classroom confirmed that the curriculum is considered the only source of knowledge and the official teaching learning document. It defines what knowledge is and how it is acquired. This is the metaphysical and epistemological demarcation which constitute a barrier to thinking autonomy. Moving away from its recommendation does not seem to happen easily as it was stated by one tutor during interview:

“It is very difficult to move away from the curriculum topics and contents. This generates the problem of not respecting learners’ opinion especially if they talk about issues that were not planned by the curriculum, the authorities or the teachers. It is therefore very hard to respect learners’ views. The teacher is the one who is responsible for teaching and must finish his program.”

Top-down transmission of knowledge

On one hand, these tutors brought out one fundamental aspect of Education in Rwanda: Education is a responsibility of adults and learners are receivers of this education. This order which extends to educational matters cannot be disturbed without compromising the socio-cultural foundations behind social interactions, social status, social mobility and stratification in Rwanda. That is why, individuals under the ladder of social hierarchy cannot be the ones to set rules nor determine the course of events even with the most original inventions. The authority has the monopoly of knowledge.

The observation made in class indicated that in all cases the **curriculum experience (content and method) was not generated by student needs and interrogations but written in advance.**

This is an indication that both content and method cannot come from students. It is the mandate of the school curriculum to provide such necessities. Needs and interrogations from learners are not considered appropriate experiences that can be included in the notes that serve for evaluation because the curriculum has already predetermined such features.

However, it was observed that teachers were using the curriculum as a guide and could look for corresponding content from different manuals to provide it to students, but without planning any content that was not suggested by the main curriculum.

It was also observed that learners were not part of content construction. While implementing Learner Centered Pedagogy, tutors focused on contents which matched the curriculum’s predetermined topics and left no room for a different content that could eventually be suggested by learners’ needs.

Curriculum content vs learners’ contribution

It was observed that learners’ discussions and debates turned around teacher’s proposed topic alone. Teachers were eager to finish what they prepared. This was affirmed by tutors in the interview when they said:

“...little time provided and learners’ centered are opposed. You don’t get time to involve students. It requires more time. Some students are not considered. As a teacher you cannot follow time every time. But you remain with the problem of not finishing the program. Big content is a challenge. You cannot finish the content by learner centered...”

The data above indicates a mismatch if not a contradiction between, on one side the insufficient time allocated to the implementation and completion of the curriculum and on the other side the requirement to engage learners in discussion, participation and construction of knowledge.

The need to finish teaching all planned contents collides with the call to allow learners’ participation. This situation generates a pseudo democratic classroom where, learners’ ideas and contributions are not valued or considered. Tutors pretend to seek learners’ ideas by putting them into groups, asking them questions but finally, no student’s ideas are retained as basis for summative evaluation which measures and indicates what has been learnt. Ideas with novelty, originality could not be retained as the final content or the tutors’ summary. Classroom becomes a place of agitation, a stage where the tutor is the main actor and whose voice alone is valuable while learners repeat after the tutor.

The above data about the relationship between curriculum, learner and tutor can be analyzed in what phenomenology calls Imaginary variation, a technique used in eidetic reduction. It consists of asking a variety of

metaphysical questions seeking to understand the essence of something. In the above case, what is necessary for the Rwandan curriculum to be perceived as the Rwandan curriculum? In terms of their subjective experience, what makes the tutors' consciousness of the implementation of curriculum content in Rwanda different from their consciousness of contents delivered under learners' authentic participation in knowledge construction? Would it still be the same curriculum if the content was set by learners' needs? If learners became more active and stopped to act as a passive consumers? If learners' ideas that are not in conformity with the curriculum were retained as part of content? Would it still be the same curriculum if teachers permitted creativity and innovation beyond curriculum requirements? If students generated original ideas in it to be considered for evaluation? If content and method were generated by learners' needs? The answers to these questions revealed the current nature of curriculum, or else its essence. This is in phenomenology an account of how noema (the object of consciousness: the curriculum) and noesis (the teacher's act of consciousness: influenced by the Rwandan culture) cohere and unfold during the curriculum implementation in ways that are both invariant and necessary to it. Concretely, this speaks to the fact that the Rwandan curriculum has features that prevent its implementation to generate thinking autonomy among learners. These features include: 1. a large suggested content which does not match the allocated time for its implementation in a learner centered mode. 2. A cultural context for which thinking is too structured to be autonomous. 3. A Pseudo implementation of learner centered pedagogy. 4. A resistance or lack of willingness and need for both learners and tutors to be original.

Without contradicting what has been said, the curriculum may change in the future. Thus, in Phenomenology, the meaning and the essence of something are constantly changing with new situations given that they are world lived experiences in time and space. The above meanings are time and space dependent and may change in the future. They are constructed situated structures. They don't define the Rwandan spirit in a final and absolute manner. They are provisional and contingent meanings. In that regard, one tutor advised the following:

"Set curriculum in the way they show all the guidelines teachers can use to respect learners original ideas. Set the way to evaluate how learner centered pedagogy is implemented at school. Content should match the time. Reduce content. Few contents and active pedagogy are better than big contents with lecture."

This view confirms that tutors do not see the current curriculum as fix and final and would wish to change it.

Tutors' clock vs event orientation

From the data above, it can be asked whether learners and teachers conformed to an external measure or time (as indicated in the curriculum), or if they allowed the event at hand (learning) to unfold on its own time? (Allowing for example original knowledge to take place at any time.) Which were more important? Deadlines teaching and evaluations or relationships and interaction with learners? The observation made in class answered to this question asked by Levine by showing that the Rwandan curriculum is structured in such a way that there is more focus to clock and less focus to events. Instructional activities were not allowed to continue even when they seemed useful except in the case of homework. Boundaries between class and outside activities were clearly indicated with deadlines respected but not fluid. Procedures could not be bypassed while learners could not ignore plans (Levine, 1997). That was the essence of the observed curriculum implementation.

Discussion

A philosophical interrogation backed by personal teaching experience in Rwanda led the author to question whether a learner-centered approach is easily applicable in a context where the domination of adult-centered practice over children's contributions seems to be a cultural element and a model for socialization. The researcher investigated the interplay of power relations between tutor and learners on how implementing the curriculum allows thinking autonomy to take place in class. Tutors' narratives were collected with phenomenology to describe their firsthand experience in facilitating learner thinking autonomy.

The difficulty of using LCP (implemented as CBC) in Rwandan classes is generated by a fundamental alienation of the western way of thinking almost completely swallowed by the Rwandan cultural and social mode of operating which forces tutors to control all the teaching activities. The concept LCP (Learner Centered Pedagogy) like the concept of classroom democracy, are both used without appropriation because these are lived realities of the western world not adapted to the sub-Saharan epistemology in which knowledge production is a social and adult activity while children are the receivers. Knowledge is created by adults with sufficient authority and power that is acceptable by the cultural filter. Truth is created by the context as Gadamer would say.

When all this is tuned to African philosophy, Léopold Sedar Senghor would say: Africans are constantly resonating at the frequency of the other. There is no line between us and the object. The Western has a relationship of domination with the object while in Africa, everything is energy, mutual influence. The other moves you. We are constantly affecting each other. This is a spiritualistic world view where community is wealth while the Western is the materialistic.

In line with the above, the epistemological implication is that, LCP cannot be objectively implemented in class without colliding with the African voice to act according to the local culture. Concretely, if LCP was to be taken seriously and literally, tutors would take the risk to accept learners' ideas as they are, use them for content summary and evaluation. But why does this fail to happen? The answer was given all along this discussion and can be summarized in these words: within a hierarchically structured culture, knowledge power flows top down; is created from the top and cannot be horizontally altered, unlike the Cartesian society where knowledge dwells in no man's land between objects of knowledge and rational minds.

LCP is an approach based on western assumptions of freedom of thought, equality and solidarity. On the other hand, the sub-Saharan cultural context is characterized mostly by the assumptions that it is a hierarchical society, where community rules and directives prevail over individual reasoning and choices. In a Rwandan secondary school, firstly, the discussion between teacher and learners cannot be a discussion between equals because the teacher is the adult in charge of all topics, all discussions and all debates which converge in one direction set by the curriculum represented by the teacher. Speaking of a dialogue between equals is not only an exaggeration but also an illusion. The teacher is like a high ranked officer while learners are disciplined soldiers and followers for whom obedience not discussion is the most important virtue. Relationships are managed by top down mechanisms from teacher to learner and when it is from learner to teacher, it is only in accordance with the obedience to teacher's instruction because no teacher's explanation can be openly interrogated or checked against truth. The way learners react to teacher's discourse is contrary to the philosophical disposition of questioning, doubting, critiquing, which represent what thinking is. Learners attitudes are characterized by obedience and trust to teacher's content which has absolute authority.

Secondly, when freedom to think and decide for self is considered in the western connotation of individual autonomy, there is no such value in a context where social and cultural stratifications define without ambiguity what an individual contributions and roles are against social prescriptions and prohibitions. The status of learners gives them a role that shows them what to say, what to do, what to think and would not allow them to move out of the context and think independently without consideration of social and cultural norms. These boundaries cannot be crossed without consequence and therefore they determine to a great extent the permission and the level at which a learner can produce originality, creativity, innovation or novelty. Probably, the cultural dynamics that motivate the teachers and the learners in a sub-Saharan cultural context are not fertile grounds for innovation and novelty in the strict Western conception.

Thirdly, the value of solidarity as a democratic prerequisite is culturally acceptable and approved. This third value is the only one that learners in Rwanda can exercise fully. They can collaborate and share acceptable ideas and values. The problem however remains that, in most cases observed, the teacher shares and the learners share what the teacher has shared. They don't share their own independent views disconnected from teacher's topic or from the cultural context.

The learner and the teacher are products of an underlying cultural structure which determines in advance what it means to be a teacher and a learner in this particular context, regardless of the requirements to use new pedagogical approach. On one hand, either school culture should forcefully shift to western values and allow learners to express independently all their minds' potentials to unleash novelty or else accept that LCP is not appropriate for sub-Saharan Africa and continue to use lecture methods. On the other hand there seems to be an urgent need to revisit how to reconcile the western and the sub-Saharan culture in the use of LCP.

Conclusion

In the Rwandan context, the author assumes through the interpretation of tutors experience that thinking takes place through a particular template, a cultural, a moral and a political structure which filter for the individual what is good or bad, useful or not, true or false. Classroom experiences are not exception at all, although the existing curriculum aims at ideals of thinking autonomy. Phenomenology enabled the author to determine that thinking is not a purely chosen individual experience but an activity conditioned by a community moral and cultural template which is both an opportunity and a barrier to the kind of thinking autonomy thought by Kant as self-governed principles or by Descartes as "the Cogito ergo sum", I think, therefore I am. LCP and CBC in particular are not culture free approaches and therefore cannot be implemented without serious challenges if the political, the ethical and perhaps most importantly the epistemological concepts' relationship between Western and Sub-Saharan African cultures are not successfully reconciled.

Recommendations

To curriculum designers and political authorities:

A study is needed on how to suit any new teaching approach to the Rwandan cultural beliefs of both teachers and learners.

Beside pre-determined content, approaches and directives, room should be open for teacher's and learner's originality, creativity, innovation and creation outside the formally set schedule.

Project based approaches, entrepreneurship and individual vocation should be given more importance than pre-established agendas.

To teachers, learners and school authorities:

Learning, knowing, solving existing problems are more important than teaching, directing, unexamined and uncritical implementation of formal documents, rules and regulations. School mandate should not forget this philosophy while focusing on learner's intellectual, moral, emotional and physical growth.

The Rwandan cultural context should not be ignored while implementing western teaching approaches. Transition from teacher to learner centered should not be taken for granted and instead, adaptation of learner centered approaches to the local context and to individual teacher and learner experience should be given due attention and time

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